

Literary Mastery

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Abstract:

The topic of Navoi and Ubaydi has always been considered significant, as exploring it in depth is essential for understanding Ubaydi's role both as a successor of literary traditions and as a unique poet in his own right. This scholarly article analyzes Ubaydi's poetry.

Keywords: Ubaydi, classical poetry, source, Sufism, poetry, genre

Introduction

Uzbek classical poetry predominantly relies on tradition in terms of form, theme, and expression. Consequently, the poetry collections (*divans*) of many poets display notable similarities, both in terms of ideas and themes as well as in form and imagery. This observation also applies to the works of Ubaydullah Khan Sultan Mahmud oğlu, a member of the Shaybanid dynasty, who wrote under the pen name *Ubaydi* in Uzbek, Persian, and Arabic.

Results and Discussions

As noted in historical sources such as *Nafā'is al-Ma'āsir al-Turki*, *Tarikhi Shaybaniy Khan*, *Muzakkir al-Ahbab*, *Majma' al-Fusaha*, *Haft Iqlim*, *Tarikhi Salimi*, and others [1], Sultan Mahmud ibn Shah Budagh ibn Abulkhair Khan requested the renowned Sufi leader of the time, Khoja Ubaydullah Ahrar, to name his newborn son. Khoja Ubaydullah bestowed his own name upon the child, naming him *Ubaydullah*.

As emphasized by the historian Mirza Haydar Dughlat, Ubaydi exhibited exceptional qualities from an early age and received education and upbringing from prominent scholars of his time, such as Amir Abdullah Yamani, Khoja Muhammad Sadr, and Khoja Mullah Isfahani. His significant achievements in knowledge, culture,

and creativity were especially praised by Hasan Khoja Nisari.

After the death of his father, Sultan Mahmud, in 1504, Ubaydi ascended the throne of Bukhara at the age of 18. During his reign, the material and spiritual conditions of the people of Bukhara significantly improved, and construction and urban development flourished. It is not surprising that Mirza Haydar likened Bukhara of that period to Herat during the times of Hussein Bayqara and Navoi.

Another aspect of Ubaydi's personality and creativity parallels that of Hussein Bayqara. Literary scholar N. Kamilov states, "Navoi regarded dervishes, after God and the Prophet, as intermediaries between humanity and Allah, as the spiritual guardians of humanity." In one of his ghazals, Navoi praised Hussein Bayqara, emphasizing that his highest moral quality was his dervish-like nature:

*Kings are dervishes, and dervishes are the kings of kings,
To him, kingship is form; to him, dervishhood is essence.*

Similarly, despite being a ruler, Ubaydi naturally inclined toward asceticism and dervishhood. When Fakhr Herati encountered him in Herat, he described Ubaydi as "a king in dervish attire." The poet himself expressed this sentiment as follows:

*I am a dervish, content with my own state, O servant Ubaydi,
A hundred thanks that I am not the sovereign of Kabul and Jam.*

In another ghazal, Ubaydi glorifies dervishhood in general:

*It is a sign for those who seek the vision of God,
That they abandon all but God, eternally—the dervishes.*

Naturally, Sufi sources have presented numerous reflections on dervishes. However, in his desire to see a king in the guise of a dervish and a dervish in the visage of a king, Ubaydi aligned with Navoi's perspective.

The sheer volume of Ubaydi's poetic works—more than 300 ghazals in Turkish, 170 in Persian, and over 430 rubaiyat in Uzbek, alongside 15 in Arabic and over 400 in Persian—testifies to his prolific creativity.

For Ubaydi, poetry was not merely a hobby or a means to achieve fame. He approached the labor of knowledge and creativity with great rigor and responsibility. As a result, he drew inspiration from and studied the works of prominent

representatives of Persian poetry, such as Hafiz Shirazi, Saadi, and Kamal Khojandi; the founder of Arabic poetry, Hassan ibn Thabit; and Uzbek poets like Lutfi, Atayi, and Gadoyi. Ubaydi paid special attention to the works of Khoja Ahmad Yasawi, the founder of early Turkish tariqa and Sufi poetry, creating *hikmats* in the Yasawi tradition. In some of his ghazals and rubaiyat, Ubaydi, inspired by the worldview of Sultan-ul-Arifin, reflected on life events and offered the following conclusions:

*Days of joy will eventually turn into sorrow,
Every pleasure will bring a hundred pains and anguish.
Do not give your heart to anything in this world,
For know that all its wealth will one day turn to nothing.*

When examining Ubaydi's works across various genres, it becomes evident that he was closely connected to Navoi and consistently regarded him as a principal mentor. This truth is aptly captured in the following couplet by Ubaydi:

*Writing poems, Ubaydi follows Navoi's verse,
In the realm of poets, he will certainly become one of them.*

Ubaydi's poetry embodies themes of justice, compassion, and truth, echoing Navoi's moral and philosophical principles.

Indeed, simplicity and brevity are dominant features of Ubaydi's poetry. His divan contains only a few ghazals of seven couplets, with most comprising five couplets. These ghazals captivate readers with their vivid metaphors, wordplay, and diverse imagery. From poetic experience, it is well known that a talented poet never blindly imitates a mentor but instead deeply analyzes the works of predecessors and strives to uncover new dimensions of the subject.

Undoubtedly, for Ubaydi, to "measure up" to Navoi was not an easy task. Nor did he ever seek to do so. However, he did not consider the act of drawing inspiration from Navoi's works to be a simple endeavor. In understanding and evaluating the contradictions of his time, Ubaydi seemed to regard Navoi's worldview and principles as a benchmark. In the realm of rubaiyat (of which Ubaydi composed nearly 850), he also earned recognition as a skilled poet. Even here, Alisher Navoi served as his intellectual and artistic guide. In his romantic, mystical, and rindi (freethinking) rubaiyat, Ubaydi composed verses that resonated harmoniously with his mentor's lines.

In conclusion, the subject of Navoi and Ubaydi holds great significance, and its comprehensive exploration is vital for understanding Ubaydi both as a continuer of literary traditions and as a unique poet in his own right.

References

- [1] The Manuscript Collection of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Inventory Nos. 848, 1505, 2016, 5045, 4282, 617.
- [2] Komilov, N. *Tasavvuf* (Sufism), Tashkent, 2008, p. 173.
- [3] The Manuscript Collection of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Ubaydi's Divan, Inventory No. 8931, p. 456.